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Report on Research Software Archival APIs and Connectors

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Deliverable Abstract

The FAIRCORE4EOSC report on research software archival APIs and connectors provides an overview of the technical solutions, workflows, and standards developed to improve the archiving, referencing, description, and citation of research software within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem. Building on the recommendations of the Scholarly Infrastructures for Research Software (SIRS) report, the deliverable describes the implementation of APIs and connectors that integrate repositories, publishers, and aggregators with the universal source code archive, Software Heritage, using metadata standards like CodeMeta and persistent identifiers such as SWHIDs. The report also outlines the deployment of the Software Heritage Mirror at GRNET to help ensure resilience and long-term access. The infrastructures involved include Zenodo, DANS Dataverse, Dagstuhl, Episciences, swMATH, OpenAIRE, Software Heritage, and GRNET. Finally, the report presents a roadmap for advancing standardisation and curation practices across infrastructures. This work supports greater interoperability, discoverability, and the recognition of research software as an important scholarly output within the EOSC and beyond.

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
ARDC	Archive, Reference, Describe & Cite
CFF	Citation File Format
EOSC	The European Open Science Cloud
EOSC PID Policy	The policy being developed by the EOSC PID Policy Task Force to ensure a minimum standard of performance for the PID ecosystem in EOSC
FAIR	Principles based on community expectations in respect of research outputs - findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.
FAIR-IMPACT	A EU-funded project that has as its main objectives to identify practices, policies, tools and technical specifications to guide researchers, repository managers, research performing organizations, policy makers and citizen scientists towards a FAIR data management cycle. The focus will be on persistent identifiers (PIDs), metadata, ontologies, metrics, certification and interoperability.
FAIRCORE4EOSC	The FAIRCORE4EOSC project focuses on the development and realization of core components for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).
JATS	Journal Article Tag Suite: XML format used to describe scientific literature published online
PID	Persistent identifier: generally expected to be unique, resolvable, and persistent.
RSAC	Research Software APIs and Connectors (EOSC)
RSMD	Research Software MetaData (guidelines) - refers to the FAIR-IMPACT deliverable D4.4
SIRS	Scholarly infrastructures for research software - refers to the report published in 2020
SPDX	System Package Data Exchange is an open standard capable of representing systems with digital components as bills of materials.
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)
SWH	Software Heritage
SWHID	SoftWare Hash Identifiers are designed to identify permanently and intrinsically all the levels of granularity that correspond to concrete software artifacts: snapshots, releases, commits, directories, files and code fragments.
SWORD	Simple Web-service Offering Repository Deposit is an interoperability standard developed by JISC extending ATOM.

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the activities and outcomes of Work Package 6 (WP6) “*Services and tools to archive, reference, describe and cite research software*” within the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, focused on implementing key recommendations from the 2020 [Scholarly Infrastructures for Research Software \(SIRS\)](#) report. The SIRS report outlined recommendations for fully integrating research software into the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), elevating it alongside publications and data as a first-class scholarly output and addressing gaps identified in the 2022 [EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda \(SRIA\)](#).

WP6 centered its efforts on four foundational Archive - Reference - Describe - Cite (ARDC) pillars:

- **Archiving** research software in the **Software Heritage (SWH)** universal source code archive,
- **Referencing** software artifacts through **Software Hash Identifiers (SWHIDs)** and other persistent identifiers,
- **Describing** software using standardized metadata aligned with the **CodeMeta** vocabulary, and
- **Crediting** software authors through robust citation mechanisms.

To achieve these goals, WP6 delivered two key components:

- The **Research Software APIs and Connectors (RSAC)**: A set of APIs and Connectors implemented in scholarly repositories, open-access publishers, and aggregators to integrate with Software Heritage
- The **Software Heritage Mirror (SWHM) at GRNET**: safeguarding against information loss and ensuring long-term, reliable access by hosting a full replica of the archive, strengthening the resilience and global reach of this essential digital commons.

WP6’s achievements were implemented in leading infrastructures such as **Zenodo**, **DANS’s** Dataverse instance, **Dagstuhl**, **Episciences**, **swMath**, and **OpenAIRE**. Each initiative produced detailed technical specifications and practical tools to improve archiving, metadata management, and citation of research software across the scholarly landscape.

The outline of the deliverable is as follows: Chapter 1 introduces the context, challenges, and the added value created within the FAIRCORE4EOSC project for software as a scholarly output. Chapter 2 provides an overview of the development methodology and processes adopted, focusing specifically on the SWH API. Chapter 3 details the developed APIs and connectors across different infrastructures, organized into scholarly repositories (InvenioRDM and DANS Dataverse), publishers (Dagstuhl and Episciences), and aggregators (swMath and OpenAIRE). Chapter 4 introduces the EOSC SWH Mirror, while Chapter 5 addresses lessons learned from the component integration and interoperability. Finally, Chapter 6 discusses the impact, sustainability, and future directions of the project activities, concluding with references in Chapter 7.

By developing these components, WP6 made a substantial contribution to advancing the goals outlined in the SIRS report and bringing the SRIA vision to life. These efforts have strengthened the foundation for a more FAIR and interconnected European research ecosystem, ensuring that research software is properly archived, referenced, described, and cited as a first-class scholarly output. These achievements not only address key infrastructure gaps but also support the broader cultural shift toward recognizing research software as a first-class scholarly output, laying the groundwork for future innovation, sustainability, and adoption across the EOSC and beyond.

1. Introduction

Software plays a critical role in modern scholarly work, enabling data analysis, modelling, simulation, and the reproducibility of results across nearly every scientific field. Without software, many research discoveries would simply not be possible. However, despite its central importance, software has historically been undervalued in research assessment and infrastructure, often lacking proper archiving, identification, and recognition. Treating research software as a first-class research output — alongside publications and data — is essential to ensure its long-term preservation, ensure reproducibility, enable reuse, and give proper credit to its creators.

Figure 1: Ensuring preservation of different scholarly outputs in Open Science: Open Datasets repositories, Open Access repositories and Open Source repositories

Several key policy drivers and international initiatives are advancing the recognition of software as a first-class output. The [UNESCO recommendations on Open Science](#)¹, highlights the importance of software in increasing open, transparent, and reproducible research. The [DORA declaration](#)² (Declaration on Research Assessment) and [CoARA](#)³ guiding principles call for broadening research evaluation practices beyond publications, explicitly recognizing outputs like software. Furthermore, the [ADORE.Software](#)⁴ declaration calls to sustain and support research software. At the national level, open science policies — such as France’s [French national plan for Open Science](#)⁵ — emphasize the need to value and preserve software alongside data and publications. These initiatives reflect a growing global consensus on the essential role of software in academia.

“Software should be considered a legitimate and citable product of research.” — [Software citation principles](#)

1.1 Context and background in EOSC

In the 2022 EOSC SRIA ([DGRI European Commission & EOSC Executive Board, 2022](#)), research software is recognized as a critical element for building a FAIR and open European research ecosystem. The SRIA calls for coordinated efforts to strengthen metadata standards, persistent identifiers, and software preservation practices. It envisions a new generation of open science infrastructures that seamlessly

¹ <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/about>

² <https://sfedora.org/read/>

³ <https://coara.eu/agreement/the-agreement-full-text/>

⁴ <https://adore.software/declaration/>

⁵ <https://www.ovvri.lascience.fr/second-national-plan-for-open-science/>

integrate documents, data, and software — enabling researchers to access and reuse scientific outputs more effectively and reliably.

In alignment with the EOSC SRIA vision, the 2020 [Scholarly Infrastructures for Research Software \(SIRS\)](#) offers concrete, actionable recommendations to close the gaps in how research software is archived, referenced, described, and cited. Aligned with initiatives like DORA and CoARA, the report highlights that software can have a significant impact beyond academia — an impact that traditional citations often fail to capture.

“scholarly infrastructures that support software source code written in academia must go the extra mile to ensure they adopt standards and provide mechanisms that are compatible with the ones used by tens of millions of non-academic software developers worldwide. They also need to ensure that the large amount of software components that are developed outside academia, but are relevant for research activities, are properly taken into account.” Figure 1 illustrates the connected ecosystem, showing how key infrastructures such as Scholarly Repositories, Publishers, Aggregators, and the universal source code archive interact at the service of the scholarly ecosystem.

Figure 2: Diagram from the SIRS report on the architecture of interconnected scholarly infrastructures

The **SIRS report** directly shaped the strategic goals of Work Package 6 (WP6) within the FAIRCORE4EOSC project. FAIRCORE4EOSC’s mission is to deliver interoperable services and tools that make research outputs — including data, publications, and software — **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR)** in different disciplines. By addressing gaps in metadata management, persistent identifiers, and interoperability, FAIRCORE4EOSC strengthens the EOSC ecosystem and supports the broader vision of an open, collaborative, and FAIR European research landscape.

1.2 The challenge / why it matters

Despite its central role in research, the way software is currently archived, described, referenced, and cited remains fragmented and inconsistent. Research software is often stored on personal websites, institutional servers, or code hosting platforms without reliable long-term preservation. Metadata describing software is frequently absent, incomplete, or non-standardized, making it difficult to understand, evaluate, or reuse. Persistent identifiers, essential for linking software to related research outputs, are not uniformly applied, and formal mechanisms for citation and credit are often missing in research workflows.

These gaps create significant challenges for the research ecosystem. **Interoperability** between different infrastructures is limited. Poor or inconsistent metadata reduces **discoverability**, leaving important research

tools hidden from researchers, catalogs, and search systems. Without stable archiving and identifiers, the **sustainability** of software as part of the scholarly record is at risk, affecting reproducibility and long-term access. Software collapse, as described in Hinsen, 2019 — the progressive failure of software due to unmaintained dependencies and shifting technological foundations — threatens the long-term usability and reproducibility of research tools.

Figure 3: Konrad Hinsen. Dealing With Software Collapse. *Computing in Science and Engineering*, 2019, 21(3), pp.104-108. [10.1109/MCSE.2019.2900945](https://doi.org/10.1109/MCSE.2019.2900945). (hal-02117588)

Addressing these challenges goes beyond infrastructure — it also requires a **cultural shift** in how the research community values software. Recognizing software as a scholarly output means encouraging good documentation, applying persistent identifiers and adopting best practices, such as the Research Software MetaData guidelines⁶ (Gruenpeter et al., 2023).

1.3 The value and purpose of the RSAC and SWHM components

Building an interconnected ecosystem requires a coordinated effort and will result in more resilient and sustainable infrastructures. While policy and technology may change, the assurance that research outputs — including software — are preserved, discoverable, and reusable over time provides lasting value. This foundation supports the continuity of scientific knowledge, enables collaboration between communities, and ensures that future generations can build upon today’s discoveries without barriers.

FAIRCORE4EOSC aims to address the fragmentation and inconsistency in software archiving and metadata practices by establishing shared frameworks and standards. Recognizing that enabling future generations to build upon today’s discoveries without barriers requires code to be openly accessible, reusable, and distributed under appropriate licenses, the WP6 partners have implemented the four concrete pillars identified in the SIRS report:

- **Archiving** software in the universal source code archive, SWH
- **Referencing** the software artifacts with the SWHID identifier, and using extrinsic identifiers for the metadata record identification
- **Describing** software with relevant properties, aligning with the CodeMeta vocabulary
- **Crediting** authors by providing mechanisms for software citation to ensure proper credit

⁶ <https://fair-impact.github.io/RSMD-guidelines/>

These four pillars were translated into two key components developed within the FAIRCORE4EOSC project:

1. The RSAC: Research Software APIs and Connectors
 - The RSAC collection of APIs and connectors integrate scholarly repositories, open-access publishers, and aggregators with the SWH universal source code archive.
 - The connectors leverage the CodeMeta metadata standard and Software Hash intrinsic Identifiers (SWHIDs) to ensure interoperability and the persistent identification of software artifacts, while exposing identifiers and metadata formats to enhance discoverability and attribution.
2. The SWHM: Software Heritage Mirror at GRNET
 - The GRNET mirror helps safeguard against information loss and ensures long-term, reliable access to humanity's software heritage.
 - By hosting a full replica of the SWH archive, GRNET reinforces the resilience and global reach of this essential digital commons.

“Let us save what remains: not by vaults and locks which fence them from the public eye and use in consigning them to the waste of time, but by such a multiplication of copies, as shall place them beyond the reach of accident.”

— Thomas Jefferson

The spirit of the Jefferson quote is aligned with the spirit of WP6: preserving research software not by locking it away, but by multiplying copies, connecting systems, and ensuring it remains accessible, citable, and beyond the reach of loss or accident.

1.4 The WP6 partners

The accomplishments of WP6 were achieved collaboratively and organized across five main tasks:

T6.1 API and Connectors Between Scholarly Repositories and Software Heritage

- Lead: CERN | Partners: KNAW-DANS, GWDG, INRIA, FONDATION INRIA, DATACITE.
- Develop API and connectors between Scholarly Repositories and Software Heritage to support archival, reference, description, and citation. Integrate and showcase the above into operational infrastructures that are used by research communities.

T6.2 API and Connectors Between Open Access Publishers and Software Heritage

- Lead: LZI | Partners: INRIA, FONDATION INRIA
- Develop API and connectors between publishers and Software Heritage to support archival, reference, description, and citation. Integrate and showcase the above into operational infrastructures that are used by research communities.

T6.3 API and Connectors Between Aggregators and Software Heritage

- Lead: FIZ | Partners: INRIA, FONDATION INRIA, DATACITE, LZI, OPENAIRE
- Develop API and connectors between Aggregators and Software Heritage to support archival, reference, description, and citation. Integrate and showcase the above into operational infrastructures that are used by research communities.

T6.4 Metadata and PIDs for Software: Curation and Standardisation

- Lead: INRIA | Partners: GWDG, DATACITE, CERN, FIZ, LZI

- Enhance the governance and the standardisation efforts related to the adoption of the CodeMeta into schema.org and to the ISO standardisation of the SWHIDs (the connectors in T6.1, T6.2 and T6.3 use the CodeMeta metadata schema and the SWHIDs).
- Develop curation mechanisms to ensure high quality metadata will be designed and implemented in scholarly repositories and publisher workflows in collaboration with the HORIZON-EUROPE-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01-05 project.

T6.5 Archival of EOSC-Core Software and Deployment of an EOSC Run Mirror of Software Heritage

- Lead: GRNET | Partner: INRIA, FONDATION INRIA
- Set up a SWHM to serve the EOSC community to archive the software for the EOSC-Core in Software Heritage.

Each task generated detailed specification documents, serving as blueprints for the technical implementation of APIs and connectors for respective scholarly infrastructures, such as **InvenioRDM@Zenodo**, **DANS’s Dataverse instance**, **Dagstuhl**, **Episciences**, **swMath**, and **OpenAIRE**.

Furthermore, in 2024, WP6 published Deliverable D6.1 — Report on Standardisation and Curation of Software Metadata and PIDs, presenting the standardization efforts to the Software Hash Identifier (SWHID) as an ISO standard, the CodeMeta metadata governance journey, and curation mechanisms in place in the scholarly infrastructures listed above. A complementary practical roadmap for implementing these recommendations was mapped out.

2. Development methodology and process

The development process within WP6 followed a structured, collaborative, and iterative approach, designed for transparency, to track progress, and to coordinate contributions of the partners and infrastructures. Each development component — such as connectors between scholarly repositories, publishers, aggregators, and the SWH archive — was managed by the service provider.

Figure 4: The FAIRCORE4EOSC WP6 components integration

The development process was supported by a combination of specification documents, GitHub repositories, test scenarios, and access rights to the SWH staging and production instances. User acceptance tests and

automated integration tests were used where applicable, ensuring quality and interoperability. Coordination across partners — including CERN (InvenioRDM), KNAW-DANS (Dataverse), LZI (Dagstuhl), INRIA (representing Episciences), FIZ (swMath), OpenAIRE, and GRNET (mirror deployment) — was essential to align efforts and timelines.

The table below summarizes the key details of each RSAC implementation and the TRL levels for each implementation, including its code repository, documentation, and service access link. It offers a practical entry point for developers, integrators, and users to explore, implement, or test the components.

TRL levels for each implementation capture their development and deployment status at the end of the project. The different TRL levels used and their interpretation are:

- **TRL7** - Release candidate, deployed in a beta testing or quality assurance environment,
- **TRL8** - Final release, not yet deployed in a production environment,
- **TRL9** - Final release, deployed on a production system available to end-users.

Where applicable, notes are provided on the future plans of each partner's roadmap regarding their development and deployment status.

Table 1: Information and links related to the RSAC components

Implementation	Code repo	Documentation	Access to service	TRL Level
InvenioRDM - SWH APIs and connectors (CERN)	Invenio-SWH GitHub repository	Zenodo Help pages	https://zenodo.org	TRL9
Dataverse - SWH APIs and connectors (DANS)	GitHub: Deposit form GitHub: MTS GitHub: ACP	https://dans-labs.github.io/swh-docs/	https://swh.dansdemo.nl/	Deposit form: TRL 7 MTS & ACP: TRL 8
Dagstuhl - SWH APIs and connectors (LZI)	https://github.com/dagstuhl-publishing/	https://github.com/dagstuhl-publishing/swh-archive-client/blob/main/README.md https://github.com/dagstuhl-publishing/swh-deposit-client/blob/main/README.md	https://github.com/dagstuhl-publishing/swh-archive-client https://github.com/dagstuhl-publishing/swh-deposit-client	TRL 9
Episciences - SWH APIs and connectors (INRIA)	https://github.com/CSDForge/episciences/issues?q=is%3Aissue+is%3Aopen+label%3AFAIRCORE4EOSC	https://doc.episciences.org/	https://epijinfo.episciences.org	TRL9
swMATH - SWH APIs and connectors (FIZ)	https://github.com/MARDI4NFDI/python-zbMathRest2Oai	https://github.com/MARDI4NFDI/swMATH4EOSC/tree/main/developer_documentation	https://zbmath.org/software/ https://oai.portal.mardi4nfdi.de/oai/OAHandler?verb=ListRecords	TRL 8

Implementation	Code repo	Documentation	Access to service	TRL Level
		https://github.com/MaRDI4NFDI/swMATH4EOSC/tree/main/user_documentation	ds&metadataPrefix=codemeta	
OpenAIRE - SWH APIs and connectors (OPENAIRE)	https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-hadoop/src/branch/beta/dhp-workflows/dhp-swh	https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/	https://beta.rdgraph.openaire.eu	TRL 8

2.1 Framework

2.1.1 Joint venture with FAIR-IMPACT

The collaboration between FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT represents a joint venture in advancing the treatment of research software as a first-class research output. As sibling projects, they combined their expertise to co-develop the Research Software Metadata Guidelines (RSMD) and contribute to the evolving governance of the CodeMeta standard. They aligned technical teams, metadata specialists, and research communities, ensuring a coherent approach to improving FAIRness for research software.

2.1.2 Development plan

The development of the WP6 components followed a structured, milestone-driven plan, ensuring steady progress from specification to production. Below is an overview of the main stages, aligned with key project milestones (MS) and deliverables (D):

- Stage 1: Specifications & Validation (M1–M7)**
 → MS30 (2022-12-22)
 Defined requirements, APIs, and user stories for the four pillars (Archive, Reference, Describe, Cite).
- Stage 2: Initial Development (M7–M15)**
 → MS31 (2023-09-29)
 Developed core components for archival APIs and connectors; published a software report detailing early outcomes.
- Stage 3: Beta Release (M15–M18)**
 → MS32 (2023-11-30)
 Released beta version of RSAC components, with extended metadata support (CodeMeta, CSL, BibLaTeX) and improved citation features.
- Stage 4: Cross-Integration (M18–M21)**
 → MS33 (2024-02-29)
 Tested interoperability across repositories, publishers, and aggregators; documented integration results.
- Stage 5: Standardisation & Curation (M21–M27)**
 → D6.1 (2024-09-30)
 Delivered report on metadata standardisation, PID use, governance (CodeMeta, SWHIDs), and curation practices.
- Stage 6: Production Release (M27–M33)**
 → MS34 (2025-02-28)
 Deployed production-ready RSAC components with full documentation and sustainability plans.

- **Stage 7: EOSC-Core Integration & Mirror Launch (M33–M34)**

→ MS35 (2025-03-31)

Connected EOSC-Core services to SWH and launched the GRNET mirror for long-term access.

2.1.3 Continuous functional review

The continuous review of specifications and releases for the FAIRCORE4EOSC RSAC components was crucial to assess their technical readiness, usability, and alignment with SIRS report recommendations before production release. This collaborative process brought together internal testers and external reviewers to identify strengths, gaps, and improvements. The main focus areas, which are detailed in the review templates in [Appendix C](#) and [Appendix D](#), were as follows:

- **Demonstrating** technical compliance, FAIR alignment, and interoperability using demo videos, sandbox environments, and documentation.
- **Validating** the archiving in SWH, correct use of SWHIDs, and proper display and export of metadata and citations (e.g., BibTeX, JSON) were verified.
- **Evaluating** the user interface (UI) for clarity, ease of use, and effectiveness in supporting workflows for researchers, developers, and institutional staff.
- **Reviewing** documentation for clarity, completeness, and relevance to target audiences, with actionable suggestions for improvement.
- **Testing** integration with other FAIRCORE4EOSC components and confirming the successful deposit of software and metadata into SWH.

Overall, the specifications review and the beta review exercises were a collaborative, discussion-driven process designed to surface strengths, identify gaps, and recommend improvements.

2.2 Metadata and PIDs for software: curation and standardisation

Task 6.4 within WP6, in parallel with T6.1, T6.2, T6.3, specifically focused on enhancing governance structures and promoting standardisation activities. It supported the creation of a governance model for the CodeMeta initiative to support the metadata schema and the ISO standardisation process of Software Hash intrinsic identifiers (SWHIDs), which was published as a formal [ISO Standard](#)⁷ in April 2025.

Additionally, T6.4 published the [D6.1 deliverable](#) (Gruenpeter et al., 2024), summarizing key outcomes: efforts towards standardization of standards like SWHIDs and CodeMeta, improved metadata curation workflows, and a roadmap for sustainable, community-driven implementation within EOSC.

2.3 Software Heritage services, features and APIs

The Software Heritage (SWH) infrastructure is a universal archive designed to collect, preserve, and share all publicly available source code. Initiated by Inria in 2015, it serves the needs of the research, public administration, and industry sectors by offering long-term access to software artifacts and all their

⁷ <https://www.iso.org/cms/%20render/live/en/sites/isoorg/contents/data/standard/08/99/89985.html>

development history. In the context of FAIRCORE4EOSC, it is the foundational infrastructure for implementing the software-related recommendations of the EOSC SIRS report.

The SWH platform provides services, features, and APIs designed to support the long-term preservation, discoverability, and reuse of software source code. Among its key services is the **Deposit Service**, which enables trusted partners to submit source code archives and metadata, ensuring proper archiving, referencing, and citation. A variety of use cases are supported, including on-demand archiving via the **Save Code Now** feature (with webhook and plugin integration), deposits of `.zip` or `.tar.gz` archives, and metadata-only submissions referencing repository URLs or SWHIDs.

As part of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, SWH has developed, refactored, and deployed key features to improve its interoperability with scholarly infrastructure, including:

1. Improvement of the existing **deposit service**
2. Creation of the **bulk save request**, tailored for aggregators
3. Creation of the **citation** UI feature and other **metadata exports**

2.3.1 Software Heritage deposit service

Unlike SWH's default **pull mechanism**, where code is harvested from public repositories like GitHub or GitLab, the deposit service uses a **push-based mechanism**. This means that partners — including repositories, publishers, and institutions — can proactively submit software and rich metadata.

Deposit partners can make initial deposits, update deposits with new versions, or enrich archived records with additional metadata. The deposit workflow uses the SWORD protocol v2.0, with endpoints for creating (**POST**), uploading (**PUT**), and tracking (**GET**) deposits. Comprehensive technical documentation and user guides are available to support integration and automation through SWH's APIs.

Example of metadata that can be provided in deposit submissions to Software Heritage⁸

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<!-- XML Entry -->
<entry xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2005/Atom"
  xmlns:codemeta="https://doi.org/10.5063/schema/codemeta-2.0"
  xmlns:swh="https://www.softwareheritage.org/schema/2018/deposit">
  <!-- SWH deposit's own properties -->
  <swh:deposit>
    <swh:reference>
      <swh:object swhid="SWHID_CONTEXT"/>
    </swh:reference>
    <!-- Metadata provenance -->
    <swh:metadata-provenance>
      <schema:url>METADATA_URL</schema:url>
    </swh:metadata-provenance>
  </swh:deposit>
  <!-- CodeMeta metadata -->
  <codemeta:name>A required software name</codemeta:name>
  <codemeta:description>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Vivamus aliquam tincidunt lacus, ut mollis tellus volutpat a. Mauris ut ornare mauris. Suspendisse elementum lacinia erat, at ornare lorem fringilla vel. Aliquam sagittis dictum cursus. Etiam in porta libero, ut malesuada augue. In viverra felis justo, a ullamcorper sem consectetur sed. Sed in euismod nunc.</codemeta:description>
  <codemeta:dateCreated>2022-11-17</codemeta:dateCreated>
  <codemeta:datePublished>2023-04-27</codemeta:datePublished>
```

⁸ <https://docs.softwareheritage.org/user/deposit/howto/prepare.html>

```

<codemeta:license>
  <codemeta:name>GNU Affero General Public License</codemeta:name>
</codemeta:license>
<codemeta:keywords>digital geometry,image processing,geometry processing</codemeta:keywords>
<codemeta:relatedLink>https://example.com</codemeta:relatedLink>
<codemeta:programmingLanguage>c++</codemeta:programmingLanguage>
<codemeta:operatingSystem>Linux, Mac OS X, Windows</codemeta:operatingSystem>
<codemeta:license>
  <codemeta:name>GNU Affero General Public License</codemeta:name>
</codemeta:license>
<codemeta:author>
  <codemeta:name>Hedy Lamarr</codemeta:name>
  <codemeta:email>email@example.com</codemeta:email>
</codemeta:author>

<!-- Versioning info -->
<codemeta:version>1.0.0</codemeta:version>
</entry>

```


Figure 5: Deposit workflow using a metadata only deposit.

How it works

Deposits are made via the **SWORD v2** interoperability protocol, which ensures standardized and reliable communication between partners' systems and the archive. The service also offers a **command line interface (CLI)** for automated integrations. The deposits include metadata in ATOM/XML format using the CodeMeta vocabulary.

Deposit partners have access to a deposit administration view that you can find in Figure 6 below.

Figure 6: Deposit administration dashboard for deposit partners and staff

2.3.2 The bulk save request API

The **bulk on-demand archival**⁹ feature in SWH enables partners and trusted users to submit large batches of software origins (such as repository URLs) for archival in a single request. Accessible through a dedicated web API (`/save/bulk/`), this service allows users to send a list of origins and visit types (in CSV or JSON format) and returns a transaction ID to track the progress of the archival process.

Once submitted, users can check the status of their requests via the `/save/bulk/<transaction_id>/` endpoint, ensuring full visibility over the loading and archival process. Depending on the implementation path, the scheduler can handle one-shot or recurrent tasks, assign priority levels, and update statuses via webhook notifications. This feature provides infrastructures with the ability to archive large volumes of software in a scalable, reliable, and trackable way, strengthening the preservation of our collective software heritage.

2.3.3 The citation feature and metadata export APIs

As detailed in the *Metadata Workflow and Architecture* document, SWH manages two types of metadata critical for citation: intrinsic metadata (embedded in the source code, like `codemeta.json` or `citation.cff`) and

⁹ <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/api/1/origin/save/bulk/doc/>

extrinsic metadata (provided externally, e.g., by publishers or aggregators). These metadata can originate from two sources: the archive itself (raw metadata) or the indexer (indexed metadata).

Metadata can be queried for specific objects using their SWHID (snapshot, release, revision, directory, content) or the repository URL (origin). When using the origin, the system returns metadata from the latest version (main branch snapshot).

Citation generation

In this first implementation, Software Heritage generates BibTeX citations from raw intrinsic metadata (codemeta.json or citation.cff) found in repositories.

- For an **origin URL**, the citation comes from the latest main branch snapshot.
- For a **snapshot, release, or revision SWHID**, it's based on the root directory's metadata.
- For a **directory SWHID with an anchor**, the citation uses the anchored version; without an anchor, it pulls from the directory itself.
- For a **content SWHID with an anchor**, it uses the repository's root metadata; without an anchor, citation generation isn't possible.

Citation architecture

SWH exposes a web API to retrieve citations:

- </api/1/raw-intrinsic-metadata/citation/origin/>
- </api/1/raw-intrinsic-metadata/citation/swhid/SWHID/>

Currently, only BibTeX (`citation_format=bibtex`) is supported.

The system uses backend utilities in `swh.web` and `swh.indexer` to extract and convert codemeta.json or citation.cff files to BibTeX format. A citation.cff file is first mapped to CodeMeta, then to BibTeX.

- No SWHID → if version exists → `@softwareversion`, otherwise → `@software`.
- With SWHID → snapshot → `@software`; release/revision/directory → `@softwareversion`; content → `@codefragment`.

Example BibTeX output

```
@software{REPLACEME,
  author = "Di Cosmo, Roberto and Danelutto, Marco",
  organization = "Inria and University Paris Diderot and University of Pisa",
  license = "LGPL-2.0-only",
  date = "2011-07-18",
  year = "2011",
  month = "07",
  repository = "git+https://github.com/rdicosmo/parmap.git",
  title = "Parmap",
  swhid =
"swh:1:snp:01b2cc89f4c423f1bda4757edd86ae4013b919b0;origin=https://github.com/rdicosmo/parmap"
}
```

Citation User Interface

A new "Citation" tab is available under "Permalinks" in the web application, making it easy for users to access and export citations.

Figure 7: Citation feature UI

For more information, the full documentation is available on the SWH citation page¹⁰.

3. RSAC: Research Software APIs and Connectors

API and Connectors Between Scholarly Repositories, Publishers, Aggregators, and Software Heritage were integrated into the following pairs of operational infrastructures that are used by research communities (led by the organization shown in parentheses):

Scholarly repositories:

- InvenioRDM - SWH (CERN)
- Dataverse - SWH (KNAW-DANS)

Publishers:

- Dagstuhl - SWH (LZI)
- Episciences - SWH (INRIA)

Aggregators:

- swMATH - SWH (FIZ)
- OpenAire - SWH (OPENAIRE)

¹⁰ <https://docs.softwareheritage.org/devel/architecture/citation.html>

3.1 Scholarly Repositories

3.1.1 InvenioRDM - Software Heritage Connector

Implementation	Code repo	Documentation	Access to service	TRL Level
InvenioRDM - SWH APIs and connectors (CERN)	Invenio-SWH GitHub repository	Zenodo Help pages	https://zenodo.org	TRL9

Architecture and design decisions

The InvenioRDM-SWH connector follows the EOSC SIRS report recommendations to integrate InvenioRDM repositories with Software Heritage's universal source code archive.

The connector addresses four main objectives:

1. Deposit software from InvenioRDM repositories to SWH, obtaining SWHIDs
2. Display SWHIDs in InvenioRDM records
3. Exchange metadata between systems
4. Support standard citation formats

The design includes workflows for depositing software bundles, handling automated deposits of new releases, and registering already archived software.

CodeMeta terms support in data model

The implementation extends InvenioRDM's data model with software-specific fields based on the CodeMeta standard. This includes support for existing bibliographic fields and adds new fields like *codeRepository*, *programmingLanguage*, and *developmentStatus*. The system also stores Software Hash Identifiers (SWHIDs) for depositions and their status as system-managed properties.

Software Heritage deposition workflows

The integration uses the SWH SWORD deposit API to send software when submissions are published for the first time. The connector tracks and displays the archival status of software deposits to SWH, giving users transparency about whether their code has been successfully archived. The integration handles two core user submission workflows: Direct deposit of a software bundle through the scholarly repository (Figure 8) and the Automated deposit of software forge releases into the scholarly repository (Figure 9).

Figure 8: Direct deposit of a software bundle

Figure 9: Automated deposit of software forge releases

User interface and experience considerations

The deposit form includes the software-specific fields aligned with the aforementioned CodeMeta terms. To ensure correctness of user input and metadata quality, the following validation approaches were applied:

- The “Repository URL” (*repositoryURL*) field is verified for being a valid URL
- The “Programming language” (*programmingLanguage*) field values are auto-completed from a pre-populated vocabulary of programming languages, harvested from [GitHub’s Linguist library](https://github.com/github/linguist)
- The “Development Status” (*developmentStatus*) field accepts values from the repostatus.org vocabulary

Software
▼

🔗 Repository URL

https://github.com/rdicosmo/parmap

URL or link where the code repository is hosted.

🔗 Programming language

OCaml ✕
✕

Repository's programming language.

💖 Development Status

Active
✕

Repository current status.

Figure 10: Software-specific fields section in deposit form

The record landing page displays SWHIDs and permalinks to the archived code, preserving the contextual information about the DOI registered as part of the InvenioRDM publishing workflow. In case of failed deposits, the user interface informs the submitter and allows repository administrators to monitor issues and take appropriate actions.

External resources

Archived in

Software Heritage

swh:1:dir:18442e0cff9fc3c7142d03f18eee1ffa02b39fcd

Available in

astropy/astropy

Release: v7.0.1

Figure 11: Display of Software Heritage identifier in record landing page

Testing and deployment status

Testing included automated tests and user sessions with researchers and repository managers. Feedback from these sessions helped refine workflows and improve error handling.

The connector is deployed on Zenodo, which serves as a production InvenioRDM reference implementation. It was announced on the [Zenodo blog](#) on October 21, 2024.

Impact

The InvenioRDM-SWH connector delivers significant benefits for researchers and the broader scientific community. Users gain confidence knowing that their software is archived for the long-term in a trusted universal repository, while the seamless integration allows them to archive their software in multiple locations without leaving their familiar development environment. The implementation provides enhanced metadata capabilities through software-specific fields that improve discoverability and description of research software. These improvements collectively contribute to better reproducibility of research by ensuring that the exact software versions used in studies are preserved, properly identified, and accessible to future researchers who need to verify or build upon previous work.

3.1.2 DANS instance of Dataverse - Software Heritage Connector

Implementation	Code repo	Documentation	Access to service	TRL Level
Dataverse - SWH APIs and connectors (DANS)	DANS Deposit Form: GitHub Metadata Transformation Service (MTS): GitHub Automated Curation Platform (ACP): GitHub , Read the Docs	https://dans-labs.github.io/swh-docs/ Documentation DANS Deposit Form: GitHub , Read the Docs	https://swh.dansdemo.nl/	Deposit form: TRL 7 MTS & ACP: TRL 8

Architecture and design decisions

DANS has developed a [Deposit Form](#)¹¹ to streamline data submission to a Dataverse instance and the SWH Archive. The deposit form is a 'one-stop shop' for researchers who need to archive their dataset(s) and related software, together with their metadata. On submission of the deposit form, the dataset(s) and their related citation metadata, such as dataset authors, will be deposited into Dataverse, while the software code and its relevant software metadata, such as software authors, will be submitted to SWH for archiving. As a final result, the deposited dataset(s) in the data repository reference the associated software by its persistent identifier (PID) in the software archive (SWHID) and vice versa, the software archive references the data repository PID (DOI).

Features implemented (deposit workflow, metadata handling, etc.)

The workflow begins when a user logs into the DANS Deposit Form, completes it, and submits the deposit. The Automated Curation Platform (ACP) extracts the form fields (e.g., GitHub repository URL), processes

¹¹ <https://swh.dansdemo.nl/>

the validated deposit form data and deposits the relevant data for software archiving to SWH via the SWH API.

The ACP determines which endpoints to use and which data transformations to apply. It checks via the SWH web API whether the source code is already archived. If not, it issues a “Save Code Now” request to SWH and polls the SWH API until the archival process is complete and a corresponding SWH Identifier (SWHID), as a `swh:dir`, is available. If the code is already archived, the SWHID is retrieved directly. This identifier is saved for later reference in the Dataverse instance.

A separate service, the Metadata Transformation Service (MTS), restructures the data into Dataverse’s native format to ensure compatibility with the Dataverse REST-based API. The ACP then deposits the SWHID, relevant form fields (e.g., dataset authors, description), and uploaded file objects to the Dataverse instance.

After deposit, Dataverse mints a Persistent Identifier (PID), which — along with relevant form fields such as the software author — is transformed into CodeMeta by the MTS. The ACP submits this CodeMeta XML to SWH via the SWORD2 protocol, completing the integration cycle.

The complete process and the components involved are shown in the sequence diagram below. For clarity, authentication processes and components (e.g., Keycloak) are omitted. The research software artifact objectives described in the EOSC SIRS report — archival, reference, description, and citation — that are met in this way, are also indicated there.

Figure 12: The DANS deposit workflow using the Metadata Transformation Service (MTS)

Integration with Software Heritage API

Integration with SWH is implemented in the ACP, via mechanism plugins. Two plugins are involved in this project:

1. **API Integration:** This plugin connects to the SWH API to retrieve a SWHID by sending a POST request with the GitHub repository URL to the appropriate API endpoint.
2. **SWORD2 Protocol Integration:** This plugin connects to SWH using the SWORD2 protocol, transmitting a CodeMeta file in ATOM XML format that includes, among other metadata, the DOI of the Dataverse deposit.

User interface and experience considerations

The platform features a one-stop-shop submission form, allowing researchers to deposit both datasets and associated software in a single, streamlined workflow. This minimizes redundancy and reduces the cognitive load on users by eliminating the need for multiple submissions.

The deposit form includes:

- Progress indicators – A clear visual representation (e.g., step-by-step navigation) to help users track submission status.
- Inline validation & error handling – Real-time feedback to prevent submission errors and guide corrections.
- Tooltips & contextual help – Brief explanations for complex fields to assist researchers in providing accurate metadata.
- Form state – A user can save form state to be able to complete the unsubmitted form on a later occasion.

At time of writing, it is still uncertain what the new Dataverse architecture will look like. However, work has begun to build on the work done in this subtask. It aims to make the deposit form accessible from within a Dataverse record, as an ‘advanced function’ that can link software. This way, an archival request to SHW can be initiated by the dataset owner from an existing Dataverse record that pre-fills the known metadata fields in the deposit form. Software related pre-filled form data, like software author(s), could also be extracted from the CodeMeta file, if it is available from the supplied forge/software repository. This will make the integration even stronger and easier.

Testing and validation approach

The testing and validation approach included a thorough internal review process, with results documented in a [report as part of the internally reviewed](#) RSAC components. Testing was performed across multiple platforms — such as the [Demo SWH Deposit](#), [EOSC Dataverse](#), and the [SWH \(SWH\) staging environment](#) — to ensure comprehensive validation.

Deployment status and availability

DANS has developed a deposit form as a mechanism to validate the functionality of its backend services. While the backend services have reached at least Technology Readiness Level 8 (TRL8), the deposit form itself is still at a lower TRL. Nevertheless, both the form's code and the backend components are designed to be generic and are already in production, actively used by other applications.

Impact

The connector allows researchers to archive both their datasets and related software in one streamlined submission process. By linking Dataverse records with Software Heritage via persistent SWHIDs, it ensures long-term preservation and citability of research software. Users can manage everything from a single interface, with helpful guidance and metadata support, improving reproducibility and reducing the burden of multiple deposits. This makes it easier for researchers to follow best practices for sharing and documenting their software.

3.2 Publishers

3.2.1 Dagstuhl - Software Heritage Connector

Implementation	Code repo	Documentation	Access to service	TRL Level
Dagstuhl - SWH APIs and connectors (LZI)	https://github.com/dagstuhl-publishing/agstuhl-publishing/swh-archive-client/blob/main/README.md https://github.com/dagstuhl-publishing/swh-archive-client	https://github.com/dagstuhl-publishing/swh-archive-client/blob/main/README.md https://github.com/dagstuhl-publishing/swh-deposit-client/blob/main/README.md	https://github.com/dagstuhl-publishing/swh-archive-client https://github.com/dagstuhl-publishing/swh-deposit-client	TRL 9

Implementation	Code repo	Documentation	Access to service	TRL Level
	https://github.com/dagstuhl-publishing/swh-deposit-client	Production Video: https://zenodo.org/records/15282586 Blog: https://www.dagstuhl.de/en/institute/news/2025/citable-discoverable-preserved-connecting-software-with-publications		

Architecture and Design Decisions

The Dagstuhl SWH Connector was developed as part of the FAIRCORE4EOSC initiative to ensure seamless archiving, discoverability, and citation of research software linked to scholarly publications. The integration extends Dagstuhl Publishing’s existing services — DSUB (submission system) and DROPS (publication platform) — with a structured mechanism for research software management.

The key objectives of this integration are:

- **Automated Archiving:** Enabling the seamless deposit of research software into Software Heritage during the publication process.
- **Persistent Identification and Citation:** Assigning SWH Identifiers (SWHIDs) to archived software and exposing them in the article’s metadata within DROPS.
- **Metadata Standardization:** Ensuring metadata consistency and interoperability using the CodeMeta schema and DataCite vocabulary.
- **Enhanced Discoverability:** Facilitating citation exports in multiple formats (BibLaTeX, CSL, codemeta.json) to increase the accessibility of research software.

Implementation and Workflow

Dagstuhl Publishing has extended its existing digital services to include the submission of research software as supplementary materials. The material is not simply published together with the scholarly article as is usually the case, but as a separate entity on the server with corresponding links to and from the scholarly article. The submission and archiving workflow follow a structured sequence (see Figure 13: Dagstuhl workflow diagram).

1. **Submission of Supplementary Materials**
 Authors are prompted to declare software artifacts during submission in DSUB. If supplementary materials exist, they must provide a URL and classify the artifact (e.g., software, dataset) using the DataCite vocabulary.
2. **Metadata Extraction and Enrichment**
 Metadata about the research software is either manually entered or automatically imported from linked repositories such as GitHub. Authors can enrich metadata by providing version details, descriptions, and author affiliations. For consistency, additionally, metadata information about the author can be copied from the main article.
3. **Editorial Review and Standardization**
 The Dagstuhl publishing team reviews the submission to ensure compliance with metadata completeness standards. Minimum requirements include a persistent URL, software classification, and structured author details.

4. Publication and Long-Term Archiving

Upon article acceptance, the research software - submitted via the submission system DSUB - is:

- published in the “ARTIFACTS” collection. This is where related research software is collected and assigned a DOI in DROPS.
- archived in SWH.
- assigned a SWHID, which is referenced in the article’s metadata.

5. Citation and Discoverability

The published software metadata is exportable in standard citation formats (e.g. BibTeX), allowing researchers to cite and reference software consistently.

Testing and Validation Approach

The integration was developed step by step and thoroughly tested by the development team. It was then introduced progressively into the live systems and revised and validated based on feedback from end users.

Deployment Status and Availability

The Dagstuhl SWH Connector has been deployed and is actively used within Dagstuhl Publishing’s infrastructure:

- **Production Deployment** – Integrated into DSUB and DROPS to support live submissions and publishing.
- **Ongoing Enhancements** – Continuous improvements based on editorial and researcher feedback.

Impact

- Software stays available long-term, even if original platforms disappear.
- Linking software to articles shows how the results were generated.
- Reviewers and readers can better verify results and understand the software context.
- Authors receive credit because archived software is citable like a publication.
- Archived software can be automatically mirrored via the SWH iframe.

Figure 13: Dagstuhl workflow diagram

3.2.2 Episciences - Software Heritage Connector

Implementation	Code repo	Documentation	Access to service	TRL Level
Episciences - SWH APIs and connectors (CCSD & INRIA)	https://github.com/CSDForge/episciences/tree/main	Documentation ¹² Video demos: Link software ¹³ Submit software to HAL ¹⁴ Blog Post ¹⁵	https://epijinfo.episciences.org	TRL9

The Episciences SWH Connector was developed by the CCSD16 to support the archiving, discoverability, and citation of research software associated with scholarly articles. This integration enhances the Episciences platform by embedding a structured workflow for referencing and presenting software as part of the publication process.

Architecture and design decisions

To promote and facilitate scientific reproducibility, [Episciences](#) now makes it easier to link an article to a dataset or software. The author submitting a document to a journal can now add the identifier provided by the platform where the data or software is stored. This facilitates access to these resources both for peers evaluating submissions and for readers if the article is published.

Features implemented

- SWHID integration
- COAR Notify¹⁷ protocol for linking research outputs hosted in the distributed network of repositories with resources from external services

User interface and experience considerations

The citation metadata of the dataset or software associated with the article is automatically retrieved by Episciences to be displayed during the peer review process and, if the article is accepted for publication, on the article landing page on the journal's website. The metadata record of the published article's DOI will contain also the data identifier like Datacite DOI or equivalent, and the software identifier, the SWHID..All this identifiers enhancing its discoverability of data and source code.

The link to the source code is based on the service provided by SWH, the open infrastructure for archiving and referencing software, which provides the SWHID already known to users who deposit their source code in HAL.

¹² <https://doc.episciences.org/software/>

¹³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ntfztp8jp90&list=PLOFm3FqS8bmYNWxrGQ2gsPK0haliR-KVq&index=3>

¹⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9guldlJTz2M&list=PLOFm3FqS8bmYNWxrGQ2gsPK0haliR-KVq&index=15>

¹⁵ <https://www.ccsd.cnrs.fr/en/2023/11/linking-your-article-with-a-dataset-or-software-its-now-easier-on-episciences/>

¹⁶ <https://www.ccsd.cnrs.fr/en/home/>

¹⁷ <https://coar-repositories.org/what-we-do/notify/>

Stéphane André ; Camille Noël - Solving viscoelastic problems in a step-inverse Laplace transform approach supplanted with ARX models: a way to upgrade Finite Element or spectral codes
 jtcam:10304

Solving viscoelastic problems in a step-inverse Laplace transform approach supplanted with ARX models: a way to upgrade Finite Element or spectral codes Preprint

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- Laboratoire Cogitamus
- Laboratoire Cogitamus = Cogitamus Laboratory

Finite Element codes used for solving the mechanical equilibrium equations in transient problems associated to (time-dependent) viscoelastic media generally relies on time-discretized versions of the selected constitutive law. Recent concerns about the use of non-integer differential equations to describe viscoelasticity or well-founded ideas based upon the use of a behavior's law directly derived from Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) experiments in frequency domain, could make the Laplace domain approach particularly attractive if embedded in a time discretized scheme. Based upon the inversion of Laplace transforms, this paper shows that this aim is not only possible but also gives rise to a simple algorithm having good performances in terms of computation times and precision. Such an approach, which fully relies on the Laplace-defined Behavioral Transfer Function (LTBF) can be promoted if it uses ARX parametric models perfectly substitutable to the real LTBF. They avoid the hitherto prohibitive pitfall of having to store all past data in the computer's memory while maintaining an equal computation precision.

Source: HAL:hal-03845394v1
 Accepted on: July 20, 2023
 Submitted on: November 15, 2022

Keywords: Laplace transform, ARX models, Iterative algorithm, Viscoelasticity, Fractional relaxation kernels, [SPL.MECA.SOLID]Engineering Sciences [physics]/Mechanics [physics.med-ph]/Solid mechanics [physics.class-ph]

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[Download this file](#) [See the document's page on HAL](#)

Software

References

archived swh:1.dir:3d4ad405846eb4dcf7ca35f9e72e85c6e817657c ¹

Software Heritage Navigating in archived swh:1.dir:3d4ad405846eb4dcf7ca35f9e72e85c6e817657c View in the archive

3d4ad40 /

File	Mode	Size
ExePaper_ConvData.mat	-rW-r--r--	1.6 MB

Permalinks

Figure 14: Dagstuhl workflow diagram

Relationships with publications - datasets - software

[Add a related work](#)

Create a relationship

Document type *

Relation type *

Software *

Figure 15: the relation modal for the article submitter on Episciences

Testing and validation approach

This has been tested by Inria's librarian team and the editorial board of the [Journal of Theoretical, Computational and Applied Mechanics \(JTCAM\)](#).

The connectors is deployed in production

Impact

The Spisciences-SWH connector helps authors link their articles to archived software using persistent SWHIDs, making source code easily accessible to reviewers and readers. This supports transparency and reproducibility while increasing the visibility of research software. Editors can also consider software as part of the submission evaluation, reinforcing its role as a key research output.

Figure 16: Deposit workflow on the Episciences platform

3.3 Aggregators

3.3.1 swMATH - Software Heritage Connector

Implementation	Code repo	Documentation	Access to service	TRL Level
swMATH - SWH APIs and connectors (FIZ)	https://github.com/MaRDI4NFDI/python-zbMathRest2Oai	https://github.com/MaRDI4NFDI/swMATH4EOSC/tree/main/developer_documentation https://github.com/MaRDI4NFDI/swMATH4EOSC/tree/main/user_documentation	https://zbmath.org/software/ https://oai.portal.mardi4nfdi.de/oai/OAIHandler?verb=ListRecords&metadataPrefix=coemeta	TRL 8

Architecture and design decisions

In swMATH, software registration follows a structured workflow addressing the four key pillars: Archive, Reference, Describe, and Cite. First, swMATH checks with SWH (SWH) via an API request to determine if the software's URL is already archived and up-to-date. If not (or if outdated), swMATH triggers an archival request, repeatedly polling SWH until the process completes. Once archived, swMATH references the software by displaying its SWH origin identifier. Next, it describes the software by depositing an XML file containing metadata in CodeMeta.json format, ensuring standardized documentation. Finally, swMATH facilitates citation by making the CodeMeta.json file available for export, enabling proper attribution. This workflow ensures long-term preservation, traceability, and academic recognition of registered software.

Figure 17: SwMath <> Software Heritage interaction workflow

Features implemented (metadata extraction, archival triggering, SWHID handling)¹⁸

- A Python script has been developed to facilitate the automated deposition of code into the designated repository, ensuring proper version control and archival compliance.

¹⁸ <https://github.com/MaRDI4NFDI/python-zbMathRest2Oai>

- An algorithm has been implemented to collect and manage SWHIDs, enabling unique and persistent identification of software artifacts.
- The system exposes SWHIDs as clickable hyperlinks, allowing users to directly access and reference software artifacts stored in the SWH archive.
- The workflow integrates XSLT transformations for Codemeta OAI metadata and deposit processes, combined with a Python pipeline to streamline data processing and ensure efficient metadata handling and code deposition.

User interface and experience considerations

- A citing button has been implemented to seamlessly integrate with biblatex-software, enabling users to generate citations for software artifacts in LaTeX documents with ease.
- A hyperlink feature has been added to provide direct access to the Software Hash Persistent Identifier (SWHID), allowing users to navigate to the corresponding software artifact in the SWH archive.

SageMath

Edit Software

swMATH ID:	825 Cite
Software Authors:	The Sage Developers ; Stein, William ; Joyner, David ; Kohel, David ; Cremona, John ; Eröcal, Burçin
Description:	Sage (SageMath) is free, open-source math software that supports research and teaching in algebra, geometry, number theory, cryptography, numerical computation, and related areas. Both the Sage development model and the technology in Sage itself are distinguished by an extremely strong emphasis on openness, community, cooperation, and collaboration: we are building the car, not reinventing the wheel. The overall goal of Sage is to create a viable, free, open-source alternative to Maple, Mathematica, Magma, and MATLAB. Computer algebra system (CAS).
Homepage:	https://www.sagemath.org/
Source Code:	

Figure 18: Metadata record in swMATH including citation functionality and source code link to the archive

Testing and validation approach

- The Codemeta implementation is being rigorously tested and validated in collaboration with the SWH team to ensure accuracy, consistency, and compliance with metadata standards.

Deployment status and availability

- Efforts are underway to coordinate with the SWH team for the bulk deposition of Codemeta files, ensuring efficient and standardized metadata submission across all software artifacts.

Impact

The swMATH–Software Heritage integration helps make mathematical software more accessible and citable - users have access to FAIR augmented records. Software entries now include reliable links to archived source code via SWHIDs, along with standardized metadata in CodeMeta format. Researchers can easily generate citations in BibLaTeX and access source code directly from swMATH, supporting better documentation, reproducibility, and long-term availability of software used in research.

3.3.2 OpenAIRE - SWH Connector

Implementation	Code repo	Documentation	Access to service	TRL Level
OpenAIRE - SWH APIs and connectors (OPENAIRE)	https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-hadoop/src/branch/beta/dhp-workflows/dhp-swh	https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/	https://beta.rdgraph.openaire.eu	TRL 8

Architecture and design decisions

The OpenAIRE-SWH connector was designed to integrate the extensive software entities already present in the OpenAIRE Graph with the Software Heritage universal archive. The architecture follows a modular, offline processing approach that efficiently handles large-scale extraction and archiving operations.

The system employs a decoupled enrichment strategy where SWHIDs are appended to software entities after successful archiving in Software Heritage. This design choice enables flexible integration with existing RDGraph data dumps while minimizing dependencies during core data updates, ensuring that the OpenAIRE Graph can continue operating independently while benefiting from enhanced software preservation capabilities.

Features implemented (metadata extraction, archiving triggering, SWHID handling)¹⁹

The OpenAIRE connector implements a comprehensive workflow that addresses the complete software archiving lifecycle:

- **Archiving workflow:** A dedicated workflow triggers the archival of software entities already included in the OpenAIRE Graph.
- **Enhanced data model:** Software entities in the OpenAIRE Graph have been extended to accommodate retrieved SWHIDs, providing persistent intrinsic identifiers for archived software.
- **Archiving requests:** The system submits "Save code now" requests to the SWH API when software entities are missing from Software Heritage or when the last visit occurred more than a specified time period (currently set to one year in the deployment).

User interface and experience considerations

The integration enhances the user experience within the OpenAIRE ecosystem by providing direct access to preserved software artifacts. The Beta RDGraph Explore portal has been enhanced to support SWHID-based search, allowing researchers to locate software using Software Heritage identifiers.

Additionally, software entities can be exported in standard citation formats, including BibTeX, through the RDGraph Explore portal, facilitating proper attribution and citation practices.

Testing and validation approach Consistency checks were performed to verify that enriched software entities conform to the RDGraph data model specifications and include correctly assigned SWHIDs. The validation process ensures that the integration maintains the quality standards of the OpenAIRE Graph while adding valuable software preservation capabilities.

¹⁹ <https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-hadoop/src/branch/beta/dhp-workflows/dhp-swh>

Deployment status and availability

The workflow that retrieves SWHIDs for software entities in the OpenAIRE Graph was merged and deployed as part of the OpenAIRE Graph Beta update, initially using a limited set of software repositories for controlled testing and validation.

Currently, SWHIDs are exposed through multiple access points: they are available when applicable through the Beta RDGraph Explore portal and accessible via OpenAIRE's API, providing programmatic access for researchers and developers building on the OpenAIRE infrastructure.

Impact

Researchers can now more easily find, cite, and trust the software linked to research outputs in the OpenAIRE Graph. Thanks to the connector, software is automatically archived in Software Heritage and assigned a persistent SWHID, ensuring it remains accessible over time. These identifiers are visible in the RDGraph Explore portal and can be exported in citation formats like BibTeX — making it simpler to include software in scholarly workflows and improve reproducibility.

4. SWHM: EOSC Software Heritage Mirror

GRNET has deployed a Software Heritage mirror, a full copy of the SWH universal source code archive, operated in agreement with INRIA. The documentation for [Software Heritage Mirror Operations](#) provided essential guidelines used to successfully deploy the GRNET mirror. A SWH mirror is an independent, complete copy of the archive. The mirror's infrastructure is designed for high availability and consists of main groups of services: **Core services**, **Replaying services**. Beyond storage, the mirror includes additional services necessary for public usability, such as a web frontend, Elasticsearch for search capabilities, and a vault service for data retrieval.

Following the guidelines, GRNET ensured adequate computing power, storage resources, and network bandwidth, along with robust IT tooling for supervision and alerting. Special attention was given to managing legal considerations, following the signature of the mirror agreement between GRNET and INRIA. The GRNET mirror maintains synchronization with the main SWH archive via a Kafka-based journal, ensuring ongoing updates and content integrity. The detailed documentation was instrumental in guiding GRNET through a comprehensive and effective mirror deployment process.

Regarding the main components of the mirror, the **Core services** form the backbone of the system, ensuring data storage, retrieving, and accessibility. This includes the deployment of a **Cassandra database cluster**, which powers the `swh-storage` service for managing metadata and relationships between software artifacts in a graph structure. This also includes the deployment of an **object storage service** (`swh-objstorage`), which handles the actual source code files (separate from the metadata). The underlying storage layer is supported by a central storage infrastructure exported through multiple NFS servers. Lastly there is also the deployment of an Elasticsearch cluster that supports the **swh-search** service by providing fast search and indexing capabilities. Additionally, the web frontend (`swh-web`) serves the main SWH web application and public API, allowing users to interact with the archive.

Alongside the Core services, the **replaying services** ensure that the mirrored data is correctly structured and verified. These include **graph replayers**, which reconstruct the relationships between different software artifacts, and **content replayers**, which validate the integrity of stored source code. To optimize performance, the number of replayers is dynamically adjusted based on demand, allowing the ingestion process to scale efficiently and improve synchronization speed with the main SWH archive. Finally, Ansible is used for the deployment of the different components.

4.1 Architecture and infrastructure setup

The mirror runs on a fleet of Virtual Machines provisioned on GRNET's high-availability cloud platform. This virtualized environment enables dynamic scalability, allowing services to grow vertically (increasing resources per VM) or horizontally (adding more nodes) in response to evolving storage demands or user load. Infrastructure provisioning and configuration management are fully automated using Ansible, with custom roles and playbooks tailored to the SWH mirror use case, ensuring consistency, maintainability, and ease of updates.

The deployment of the EOSC SWH mirror at GRNET closely followed the official guidelines provided by INRIA, the primary institution behind the SWH initiative. These guidelines offered a strong foundation for architectural design and service configuration. However, within the recommended framework, there was flexibility to make key technical choices tailored to the local infrastructure and operational goals. As such, several core components were deployed as specified, while others were selected or adapted based on performance, scalability, and maintainability considerations.

Storage Backend - NFS

At the core of the mirror's architecture is the **storage backend**, implemented using a **NetApp storage appliance** accessed via **NFS (Network File System)**. The selection was made **based on performance, scalability, and maintainability considerations**. This choice provides a **reliable and high-throughput** solution for managing large-scale archival workloads. The NetApp system is a **proven technology** that integrates seamlessly with the rest of the infrastructure, ensuring **efficient data management, scalability, and performance**. Its robust feature set and operational maturity make it well-suited to meet the demanding storage requirements of the SWH mirror.

Cassandra

One of the most critical decisions in the technology stack was the selection of the backend storage system. The mirror uses a distributed **Apache Cassandra cluster** as its primary storage backend. Cassandra was chosen for its proven ability to handle large-scale, write-intensive workloads with high reliability. Its decentralized, masterless architecture supports seamless replication across nodes, making it an ideal choice for ensuring data durability and availability in a mirror setting.

Cassandra's linear scalability allows the storage layer to grow in step with the archive, simply by adding more nodes to the cluster. This makes it well-suited for a long-term archival system like SWH, where the dataset is expected to grow continuously. In addition, the system is tuned to support high-ingestion rates required by the synchronization process (swh-sync) with the upstream archive. Routine monitoring of Cassandra includes metrics on read/write latency, compaction activity, and node health to ensure consistent performance and early detection of anomalies.

The following figure shows the different components deployed in the GRNET SWH mirror.

Figure 19: The components deployed for the GRNET - Software Heritage Mirror.

4.2 Synchronization mechanisms with the main Software Heritage archive

Software Heritage collaborates with other institutions like GRNET to maintain **mirrored or replicated nodes** for redundancy and increased availability. Mirrors are synchronized through **dedicated sync protocols** and tools developed for large-scale, distributed storage. The GRNET mirror maintains synchronization with the main SWH archive via a Kafka-based journal, ensuring ongoing updates and content integrity. The documentation for [SWH Mirror Operations](#) provided essential guidelines used to successfully deploy the GRNET mirror and the synchronisation mechanisms. The detailed documentation was instrumental in guiding GRNET through a comprehensive and effective mirror deployment process.

The synchronizations are split into the following parts

- storage
- replayers

As already mentioned, replaying services ensure that the mirrored data is correctly structured and verified. These include **graph replayers**, which reconstruct the relationships between different software artifacts, and **content replayers**, which validate the integrity of stored source code.

Mirroring the Graph Storage

The **graph storage** — typically an instance of `swh.storage` — contains the **Merkle DAG** structure representing the relationships between software artifacts in the SWH archive. This excludes the actual contents of source code files (the blobs), but remains a critical component that must be available on mirror nodes.

To replicate this structure across mirrors, SWH uses a **journal-based replication mechanism** backed by **Apache Kafka** as the event streaming platform. This journal logs all graph operations (e.g., additions of revisions, releases, directories, etc.) in an append-only format.

The **Graph Replayer** is a key component that consumes this journal and **reconstructs the graph** by replaying the streamed operations, thereby updating the mirror's local copy of the graph storage. This approach avoids the need for full data dumps and enables consistent, incremental synchronization between the main archive and its mirrors.

To further optimize performance and scalability, the number of graph replayers can be **dynamically scaled based on system load and demand**, improving ingestion throughput and ensuring timely updates to the mirror.

In the current setup, more than **200** instances of the Graph Replayer are deployed in parallel to efficiently handle the high volume of content replication.

The Graph Replayer instances send data to the **swh.storage** API workers. Currently 4 **swh.storage** nodes have been deployed. Each node runs 20 **swh.storage** API workers.

Mirroring the Object Storage

As previously mentioned, a mirror is a complete replica of the SWH archive, independently maintained by GRNET. One of the critical components required for enabling such a mirror is the object storage system, typically implemented using **swh.objstorage**. This storage holds all file content blobs corresponding to the archived source code collected by SWH. The replication of this content is orchestrated using journals, with Kafka serving as the backbone for event streaming. Notably, the **swh.journal.objects.content** Kafka topic does not carry the actual file contents. Instead, it contains metadata — such as cryptographic hashes and identifiers — describing the blobs.

To retrieve and replicate the actual blob content, a dedicated **swh-journal** client subscribes to this Kafka topic. Upon receiving the blob identifiers, it fetches the corresponding data from the main SWH object storage and stores it into the mirror's local object storage. A reference implementation of this process is provided in the Content Replayer module, which includes a command-line tool that automates this replication by consuming the Kafka stream and synchronizing content across storages. This tool is a core building block for establishing and maintaining a mirror, and is actively used by GRNET in the deployment.

In the current setup, more than **70** instances of the Content Replayer are deployed in parallel to efficiently handle the high volume of content replication. This distributed approach ensures that the mirror stays up-to-date with the upstream archive and can scale to accommodate growing data volumes as SWH continues to ingest and archive new source code.

The Content Replayer instances send data to the **swh.objstorage** API workers. Currently 3 **swh.objstorage** nodes have been deployed. Each node runs 8 **swh.objstorage** API workers.

Search Functionality

Search functionality is based on **swh-service** and an elastic search cluster. **swh-search** service runs in front of the elastic search cluster and provides a rest like API.

- **Cluster Details:**

- 6 Elasticsearch nodes
- Main index: origin
- 18 distributed shards, with replication
- Index size: 370 million documents, ~0.72 TB

The `swh-journal` client plays a key role in maintaining synchronization between the SWH archive and its indexing services. To manage high throughput efficiently, multiple instances of the client run in parallel. Each instance connects to the SWH broker network, which functions similarly to a Kafka system, and subscribes to key topics such as `origin` and `origin_visit`. These topics publish events related to the discovery and retrieval of source code repositories. By consuming these messages in real time, the `swh-journal` clients enable continuous tracking of updates, ensuring that downstream services like search and storage remain aligned with the latest state of the archive.

The data ingestion and processing workflow involves `swh-journal` clients that consume messages — representing events or changes — from the `origin` and `origin_visit` topics in the SWH broker network. Upon receiving these messages, the clients analyze their content to determine the appropriate action. If the information is sufficient, the client directly contacts the `swh-search` service to update the search index with the new or modified data. However, if additional context or metadata is needed to ensure accurate indexing, the client queries the `swh-storage` backend to retrieve the necessary artifacts before proceeding with the index update. This mechanism ensures that the search index remains synchronized with the main SWH archive in a reliable and consistent manner.

This architecture ensures **real-time or near real-time synchronization** of the search index with the **main SWH archive**, enabling fast and accurate search over hundreds of millions of archived software origins.

Table 2: Mirror components description

Component	Description
<code>swh-journal</code>	Sync client that consumes data from broker topics and updates search index
<code>swh-search</code>	Service in front of Elasticsearch, provides search API
Elasticsearch	Scalable search engine used for indexing and querying metadata

4.3 Operational considerations (performance, security, reliability)

Operating a SWH mirror requires a robust and well-architected infrastructure, with each system component provisioned for high availability, performance, and scalability. The mirror components are continuously monitored to detect performance or capacity issues, with key metrics tracked in real time to ensure consistent service levels. At the core of the mirror’s architecture lies the backend storage system, delivered via a NetApp storage appliance using NFS. This setup is proven and reliable, offering efficient data management and high throughput — making it well-suited for large-scale archival workloads. The NetApp system integrates seamlessly with the rest of the infrastructure and supports our requirements for scalable, high-performance storage. Key storage metrics — including IOPS, throughput, and latency — are continuously monitored to maintain consistent service levels. Capacity thresholds are also in place to trigger - enable proactive expansion and avoid bottlenecks.

All components of the mirror are deployed **in a highly available configuration**, ensuring that individual service disruptions do not impact the system as a whole. This includes the web front ends, background processing

services, databases, and synchronization mechanisms. Redundancy and failover capabilities are built into each layer, and load balancing is employed where appropriate to distribute traffic and processing workloads.

Beyond storage, the GRNET-SWH mirror backend systems are carefully tuned for high performance and fault tolerance. Replication and failover configurations ensure continuity of service, even in the event of hardware or software failures. Indexing operations — critical for querying and serving archival data — are optimized to function efficiently at scale. All core components are actively monitored for CPU, memory, disk usage, and responsiveness, with alerting mechanisms in place to detect early signs of resource stress or abnormal behavior, enabling swift intervention and issue resolution. Regular load testing and capacity planning are conducted to ensure the infrastructure can handle growth and peak demand. Together, these practices help maintain a resilient and responsive platform for long-term preservation and access.

Security is enforced at multiple levels of the infrastructure. All data retrieved from the upstream archive is validated using cryptographic hashes to ensure integrity. Systems are secured with strict access controls, and regular patching is performed across all layers of the stack. The mirror’s internal communication occurs entirely over a dedicated private network, which ensures isolation, improves performance, and significantly reduces the risk of external attack surfaces.

Scalability is an ongoing priority. The infrastructure is deployed on virtual machines using GRNET’s cloud infrastructure, allowing us to scale services horizontally and vertically as the archive grows or demand increases. Resource utilization is reviewed regularly to guide capacity planning. Throughout this process, we maintain close coordination with the upstream SWH team to ensure compatibility with evolving data models, protocols, and operational best practices.

4.4 Monitoring and maintenance procedures

A dedicated monitoring node runs the Prometheus service and Grafana, forming the core of our observability stack. Prometheus collects metrics from all other services in the infrastructure, enabling real-time insights into system health and performance. To enrich this visibility, we have integrated a PostgreSQL scraper that extracts operational data directly from the main PostgreSQL database and an Elasticsearch scraper that gathers metrics from the Elasticsearch cluster. For SWH-specific services, such as search, web, graph replayers, and others, we’ve deployed a statsd replacement server to which all relevant services are configured to send metrics. Prometheus scrapes these metrics at regular intervals, and Grafana dashboards provide organized, visual access to elastic, PostgreSQL, and SWH-specific service metrics.

All services and nodes are deployed and managed using Ansible, with tailored roles and playbooks developed specifically for the SWH mirror use case. This infrastructure-as-code approach ensures consistent, repeatable deployments and simplifies ongoing maintenance and updates. It also allows for quick redeployment or scaling of components while maintaining the integrity and stability of the system.

Current status and access information

The Mirror is in production, and you may access information from <https://ui.swt.grnet.gr>

Use cases and benefits for the EOSC community

GRNET’s mirror is a new addition to the global SWH network, designed to preserve and ensure open access to software source code. It strengthens software availability, protects against data loss, and guarantees that critical digital knowledge remains accessible to all. As an onboarded service to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), the GRNET mirror supports the open sharing and discovery of research software across Europe. This important step was made possible through the support of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, which funded the deployment of the mirror.

5. Lessons learned from components integration

This chapter reflects on the key lessons learned from implementing the RSAC and SWHM components. It reviews the common protocols and standards adopted, the measures taken to ensure systems work seamlessly together, and the development of reusable components that support efficient integration. The chapter also highlights the challenges and insights gained from cross-component coordination and outlines future directions to further strengthen interoperability across research software infrastructures.

5.1 Lesson 1: Cross-Infrastructure coordination starts with clear policy decisions

One of the most important lessons learned in this project is that successful cross-infrastructure coordination depends on having clear, shared policy frameworks from the outset. The **SIRS report** played a critical role in providing this foundation. It offered a well-defined set of recommendations and guiding principles for archiving, referencing, describing, and citing research software, which allowed all participating infrastructures to align their technical and organizational efforts around a common vision.

Without this top-level direction, technical efforts risk becoming fragmented, duplicative, or short-lived, leading to balkanization of the research software landscape. The fragmentation risk was mitigated thanks to the clear framework provided by the SIRS report, which helped partners across repositories, aggregators, and publishers align on interoperable solutions. Community efforts such as the SciCodes consortium²⁰ further strengthened this alignment at the international level by promoting collaboration, sharing best practices (Task Force on Best Practices for Software Registries, 2020), and advancing the adoption of shared standards across the research software landscape.

Key takeaways:

- Cross-infrastructure coordination depends not only on technical agreements but also on policy-level commitments.
- Clear, community-driven recommendations help avoid duplication of effort and instead promote mutualization of solutions, enabling infrastructures to share developments, align practices, and build interoperable, reusable components.

5.2 Lesson 2: Streamlined integration needs dedicated support and resources

The integration of the SWH deposit service across RSAC partner infrastructures required substantial technical support and coordination. Helpdesk activities played an important part in guiding partners through implementation, clarifying documentation, and addressing integration-specific questions.

A central area of support involved clarifying the use of client registration metadata, specifically the roles of `provider_url` and `domain`. Partners such as DANS sought guidance on how these properties interact, the use of DOI prefixes as `provider_url`, and the system checks performed during deposits. Updates to the documentation were made to reflect current practice, particularly around metadata-only deposits, which raised important questions on whether deposits can apply to objects not yet archived in SWH (**answer**: yes, but clients should check beforehand to avoid errors).

²⁰ <https://scicodes.net/>

InvenioRDM (Zenodo) raised important integration topics, such as lifting the 1-MB file limit, managing complex identifiers (e.g., `dir` with qualifiers like `anchor` and `visit`), and best practices for displaying SWHIDs²¹ and permalinks on landing pages. The team also engaged with SWH on aligning CodeMeta metadata mapping, updating metadata over time, improving origin linking (preferring concept DOIs), and exploring options like embedding SWH iFrames for richer software previews.

For OpenAIRE, technical consultations addressed optimizing API usage, minimizing the number of calls, and evaluating when to store SWHIDs in local systems. OpenAIRE also sought guidance on developing test cases aligned with the RSAC goals (Archive, Reference, Describe, Cite), the appropriate use of `visit_type` parameters, and handling high-volume operations under current API rate limits. Questions also emerged around the persistence of SWHIDs if repository URLs change — clarified as stable — and whether data dumps could complement or replace multiple API calls (a metadata-inclusive dataset export is under consideration).

swMath raised focused questions on ensuring the quality of CodeMeta metadata, which directed helpful discussions on available tools and best practices.

Main Helpdesk Issues Addressed

- Roles and relationship between `provider_url` and `domain` in client setup
- Use of DOI prefixes and checks performed on deposits
- Metadata-only deposits: scope, limitations, and best practices
- API usage optimization and reduction of call volumes
- Managing API rate limits in large-scale operations
- Local storage and reuse of SWHIDs by partners
- Support for CodeMeta metadata validation

Key takeaways:

- Helpdesk support is essential for smooth integration and to ensure interoperability.
- Continuous updates to technical documentation and tailored community guidance are critical for successful implementation.

5.2 Lesson 3: Beyond researchers — Strengthening institutional engagement and ensuring training

Improving research software practices requires reaching beyond individual researchers to engage the broader institutional ecosystem, including librarians, research support staff, software engineers, and repository managers. Insights from the FAIR-IMPACT RSMD guidelines show that providing clear, practical recommendations is only part of the solution — what's equally critical is building institutional capacity to implement them.

Training programs, institutional policies, and dedicated roles for curation and metadata management are essential to ensure that good practices are adopted and maintained over time. Community coordination efforts, such as those led by CodeMeta, SciCodes, FAIR4RS, and the Software Citation Implementation WG, further help align efforts across disciplines and infrastructures, reducing fragmentation and fostering interoperability.

²¹ <https://docs.softwareheritage.org/user/deposit/howto/integrations.html>

The key lesson is that advancing FAIR-aligned software practices is not just about improving tools and workflows, but about embedding knowledge, capacity, and incentives within institutions — ensuring that research software becomes a durable, well-supported part of the scholarly ecosystem.

Key takeaways:

- Institutional engagement is essential — good practices must be embedded at the organizational level, not left to individual researchers alone.
- Training and capacity building for research support staff, librarians, and IT teams are critical for sustaining the adoption of FAIR-aligned software practices.
- Dedicated roles for curation, metadata management, and technical support ensure long-term sustainability and quality of software dissemination and preservation workflows.

6. Impact, sustainability, and future directions

6.1 Outreach and impact: advancing a community-driven vision

The WP6 outreach activities were designed to engage diverse research communities, promote the adoption of project outputs, and strengthen collaboration across the research software ecosystem.

Between 2022 and 2025, WP6 organized and participated in a wide range of activities, including:

- **Workshops and webinars** (e.g., joint GRNET and SWH webinar, the SWHID standardization webinar, CodeMeta sessions, and deposit partners workshop).
- **International events and conferences** (e.g., RDA plenaries, OR2024, PIDFest, ICMS 2024, EOSC Symposium, FAIRFest, and IDCC 2025)
- **Community collaborations** with groups like the FAIR-IMPACT²² and EVERSE²³ projects, EOSC OA7²⁴ on Research Software, SciCodes²⁵, RDA SSC IG²⁶, CodeMeta²⁷, ReSA²⁸, and the mathematics community (via MaRDI and swMath).
- **Publications and white papers**, including a recommendation on citing Git links with SWHIDs in mathematics research and contributions to Zenodo and blog posts.

The outreach targeted technical and research audiences, aiming to raise awareness about the new tools and services, encourage adoption, and gather feedback for ongoing improvements.

6.1.1 Deposit Partners Workshop 2024: Advancing Research Software Preservation

The Software Heritage Deposit Partners Workshop, held on November 26, 2024, brought together stakeholders to showcase the integration between scholarly infrastructures and the universal source code archive, SWH. The event opened with a keynote by Jean-François Abramatic, highlighting the vision of the Scholarly Infrastructures for Research Software (SIRS) report and its implementation through the

²² <https://fair-impact.eu/>

²³ <https://everse.software/>

²⁴ <https://eosc.eu/opportunity-area-exp/oa7-research-software/>

²⁵ <https://scicodes.net/>

²⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/software-source-code-ig/work-statement/?sow=169734>

²⁷ <https://github.com/codemeta/codemeta>

²⁸ <https://www.researchsoft.org/#>

FAIRCORE4EOSC project. The workshop focused on the **Research Software APIs and Connectors (RSAC)** developed in FAIRCORE4EOSC, which address the four key pillars of the SIRS report. The workshop featured lively “Demo-mania” sessions, where service managers presented their integrations and shared challenges and solutions. These demonstrations underscored the critical importance of archiving research software alongside publications and data to safeguard scholarly knowledge.

Following each demo, participants engaged in feedback sessions, reflecting on how these integrations could be shared with colleagues, librarians, developers, and institutional leaders. The discussions emphasized the importance of improving metadata quality, strengthening links between publications and software, and embedding software archiving practices into organizational workflows.

Reflecting on the SIRS Journey

The workshop concluded with a reflective session using the metaphor of a “**mood boat**”, where participants assessed their progress along the SIRS recommendations and identified areas for future effort. The group reached a strong consensus on the need for continued **advocacy**, **collaboration**, and **knowledge-sharing** to ensure the recognition of software as a key research output.

6.1.2 Celebrating achievements at the FAIRFest 2025

FAIRFest 2025 took place on February 20-21 at The Hague, to celebrate the European projects FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT achievements. The event brought together the research community to discuss advancements in FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) solutions within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The achievements in research software were prominently featured, with dedicated presentations, posters, and an engaging stand at the marketplace.

Research Software at the Marketplace

At Stand 8 in the FAIRFest Marketplace, the WP6 team showcased how research software is emerging as a first-class scholarly output within the EOSC landscape. Attendees engaged with experts working on software curation, metadata, metrics, and archiving, with a key focus on building a community-driven vision to ensure sustainable software recognition.

Related links and materials from the event

For those who wish to explore further, here are key resources and recordings from the event:

- **Posters at the Research Software stand**
 - RSMD Poster²⁹
 - FC4E RSAC & SWHM Poster³⁰
- **CodeMeta – RSMD guidelines and RSAC panel**
 - Full panel video: [Watch here](#)
 - CodeMeta segment: [Watch here](#)
 - Slides: [Zenodo link \(slide 34\)](#)
- **R for Reusability panel**

²⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15072272>

³⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15072204>

- Video: [Watch here](#)
- **Additional materials**
 - Marketplace presentation³¹
 - FAIRFest Programme³²

FAIRFest 2025 had a meaningful impact by strengthening collaborations across the research software community and raising visibility around key initiatives, including the RSMD guidelines, CodeMeta developments, and SWH. The event helped broaden awareness of the challenges and solutions needed to make research software a fully integrated, FAIR component of the scholarly ecosystem.

6.2 Sustainability: Paving the way collectively

Ensuring the long-term sustainability of research software within the scholarly ecosystem requires more than technical solutions — it demands the adoption of best practices, dedicated resources, and clearly defined roles across institutions and infrastructures.

While community engagement around FAIR software solutions is growing, it is essential to broaden these efforts to reach not only researchers and developers but also librarians, research support staff, funders, and policymakers. The wider adoption of the Research Software Metadata Guidelines (RSMD), already recommended in the EOSC Federation Handbook, along with persistent identifiers and metadata standards, depends on institutional investment in training, dedicated roles, and integration into operational workflows.

Without sustained funding and formal recognition, the burden of ensuring software curation and reproducibility too often falls solely on researchers and developers, making the system fragile. Funding mechanisms must explicitly support technical experts, community managers, metadata curators, and infrastructure maintainers, whose roles are essential for long-term impact.

Looking ahead, several priorities will be vital for sustaining progress. Policy can play a decisive role by promoting shared principles, securing long-term support for open infrastructures, and ensuring ongoing investment in curation and training. It is equally important to formally recognize software development as a valued contribution in researchers' careers. And, last but not least, software developed with public funding should be open source by default, maximizing transparency, reuse, and public benefit.

In short, sustainability must be understood as a collective responsibility — supported by community, policy, and investment — to ensure that research software remains a durable and accessible pillar of open science.

6.3 Conclusion

This report concludes the work of WP6, reflecting on the collective efforts made to advance the interoperability, preservation, and recognition of research software across the European research ecosystem. Together, we have implemented a community-driven vision first laid out in the SIRS report, further informed by the SIRS Gap Analysis, and realized through the FAIRCORE4EOSC project.

The development of APIs and connectors, the integration of metadata standards like CodeMeta, the application of persistent identifiers such as SWHIDs, and the preparation of the SWH mirror at GRNET

³¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15072664>

³² <https://fair-impact.eu/fairfest-programme>

represent major milestones in this work. These achievements required substantial technical and collaborative effort across diverse partners and infrastructures and have contributed to building a more connected, interoperable ecosystem for research software.

We acknowledge the dedication and contributions of all partners that made these accomplishments possible: CERN, INRIA, Fondation Inria, FIZ Karlsruhe, KNAW-DANS, LZI, OpenAIRE, GRNET, DataCite, GWDG, and the wider scholarly community, as well as the infrastructures they represent — including Zenodo/InvenioRDM, Dataverse, Dagstuhl, Episciences, swMath, and the OpenAIRE Graph. Their expertise, engagement, and collaborative spirit were essential in bringing the SIRS report vision to life.

Looking ahead, several use cases and ongoing deployments may support future success stories. These include the automated archiving of software associated with publications, the integration of SWHIDs into repository workflows for persistent referencing, and the display of machine-readable software citation formats to support reproducibility and proper credit. Such developments are expected to benefit researchers and contribute to the broader scientific ecosystem.

Extending these efforts internationally, by aligning with global initiatives and emerging policies, will help ensure lasting impact at an international level.

While significant progress has been made, the path toward full adoption and sustainability remains ongoing. Long-term success will depend on continued community efforts, institutional support, and adequate funding to ensure that research software is preserved, discoverable, and properly credited as a first-class research output. This joint endeavor has laid a strong foundation for future progress within EOSC and beyond.

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No	Description/Link
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R3	Di Cosmo, R., Gruenpeter, M., & Zacchiroli, S. (2018). Identifiers for Digital Objects: The Case of Software Source Code Preservation. 1–9. https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/KDE56
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R13	Katz, D. S., & Barker, M. (2023). The Research Software Alliance (ReSA). Upstream. https://doi.org/10.54900/zwm7q-vet94
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R15	Mayernik, M. S. (2016). Research data and metadata curation as institutional issues. <i>Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology</i> , 67(4), 973–993. https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23425
R16	Rios, F. (2018). Incorporating Software Curation into Research Data Management Services: Lessons Learned. <i>International Journal of Digital Curation</i> , 13(1), Article 1. https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v13i1.608
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Appendices

Appendix A: SIRS Gap report analysis and RSAC solution (partly reused from D6.1)

Table 3: SIRS Gap report analysis and actions

Dimension	Associated stakes	Gap, threat	Action point	Comment
Archive	Enabling long-term access to software source code	Software source code not archived: software is out of the scope of the institutional repositories and national archives	Using the SWH API to ensure source code archiving	Long term access to software source code raises also governance stakes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - infrastructures should be built from stable existing open source software building blocks - the infrastructure should be hosted and run by a non-profit organization to avoid risk of proprietarisation
Archive	Intrinsic metadata should be created and stored according to recognised best practices in software development because they may provide information about the versioning, the relations with other outputs and other identifiers	Metadata describing software not archived	Using the SWH API to ensure metadata archiving	In addition, metadata should be available under a CCO license
Reference	Improving reproducibility of research by pinpointing the exact version of any software artifact via intrinsic identifiers	Lack of common identifiers for software: referencing and describing software are separate concerns. Inconsistent use of PIDs complicates the unique identification of software and the proper attribution of credits.	Requiring using SWHIDs in software sustainability plans for project proposals	

Dimension	Associated stakes	Gap, threat	Action point	Comment
Describe	Providing software descriptions to improve their citability and their discoverability	Lack of support to keep and maintain intrinsic metadata	Adoption of guidelines and common software metadata quality indicators is needed	Aggregated metadata should be available “as open as possible as closed as necessary” (e.g. to respect GDPR regulations)
Describe		Lack the adoption of a <i>common software metadata schema</i>	Encourage use of CodeMeta, funding for community and governance	
Describe		Aggregators rarely provide access to the metadata and data through an open API		
Credit	Software heavily relies on collaborative work and different types of contributions: coding, debugging, testing, designing, etc.	Lack of a standardized taxonomy for research software contributor roles to categorize contributions	Generalization of Contribution Role Ontology (CRO) and integration in Codemeta.	
Credit		No common software citation practice adopted in infrastructures: software citation practices are not standardized and very often, software is not considered as a citable output	Require adoption of standards like CFF.	
Credit		No common software quality indicators and best practices for software metadata	Development of common software indicators, guides based on Codemeta	
Governance and sustainability		No adoption of SIRS recommendations from infrastructures	Require governance and sustainability to be part of the software management plan. Compliance with best community practices	
Publishers platforms	Adoption of SIRS recommendations by publishers		Working Group to synchronize and ease the adoption of community	For now, specialized publishers are the ones who have mostly changed their practices: support for

Dimension	Associated stakes	Gap, threat	Action point	Comment
			standards into JATS: see JATS4R recommendation for software https://jats4r.niso.org/software-citations/	software outside of specialist journals is still limited. But a general effort is required, to implement standardized practices, but it must be as acceptable as possible for all the stakeholders.

Appendix B: Description of Infrastructures Types from FAIR-IMPACT D4.4

Table 4: Definition and examples of existing infrastructures and platform types

Scholarly infrastructure	Definition/ Why do we focus on this actor/infrastructure?	Examples
Scholarly Repositories	<p>“An organisation called to archive and make available research artifacts, e.g. articles, datasets, software.” (EOSC Executive Board & EOSC Secretariat, 2020)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HAL • Zenodo • Dryad • Dataverse
Publishers	<p>“Any organization that prepares submitted research texts, possibly with associated source code and data, to produce a publication and manage its dissemination, promotion, and archival process.” (EOSC Executive Board & EOSC Secretariat, 2020) “[...] there is an opportunity for publishers to educate authors on the necessity of sharing software source code and encourage a standard workflow.” (EOSC Executive Board & EOSC Secretariat, 2020)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dagstuhl • IPol
Aggregators	<p>“Aggregators collect, curate, select, present, and aggregate information about research software from various sources to improve findability in diverse communities.”(EOSC Executive Board & EOSC Secretariat, 2020)</p> <p>“Any service that collects information about digital content from a variety of sources with the primary goal of increasing its discoverability, and possibly adding value to this information via processes like curation, abstraction, and classification, and linking.”(EOSC Executive Board & EOSC Secretariat, 2020)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OpenAIRE • swMATH.org

Appendix C: Review grid of the RSAC components specifications

Table 5: Reviewing grid explanation

Section	Subsection	Suggested usage	The question to answer
Overview		Text from proposal	
Objectives	Archive	Archive	
	Reference	Reference	
	Describe	Describe	
	Cite	Cite	
Out of Scope		Identify elements in the proposal that are out of scope for this particular subcomponent And identify other limitations due to resources or feasibility	What are the limitations of the subcomponent in achieving the 4 pillar objectives- archive, reference, describe and cite?
Requirements	User stories	As a __ I can ___ so that ___	What is the user's story? Why does this user want to achieve a particular goal?
	User requirements	Identifying the needs, goals, and tasks directly from the SIRS report	What is the user's need to achieve the goal and have a happy ending?
	Functional requirements	Identification of application requirements, server, database, etc..	What does the system / infrastructure can provide as new or improved functionalities to obtain the happy ending?
	Non-functional requirements		What does the system / infrastructure can provide as non technical additions to obtain the happy ending?
Specifications	Architectural design	Sequence diagram	What components are related and what is the workflow to obtain the objectives?
	Functional specifications	A breakdown of the implementation function: capabilities, appearance, and interactions with users in detail for software developers (equivalent to a issue / ticket / task that can be resolved with one PR / diff)	What will the subcomponent team implement as part of the infrastructure features/functionalities to answer the identified requirements?
	Service specifications		How do I test that the service is working properly?

	Operational specifications		
	Integration with EOSC Core components	List the FC4E CC with links to each specs and identify the points of integration / interoperability	How does this subcomponent interact with each one of the FC4E Core Components?
External references	implementation infrastructure	Relevant documentation on infrastructure website	Where can I get more information about the implementation's current state?
	Software Heritage	Relevant documentation on SWH	Where can I get more information about the SWH archive's current state?

Appendix D: Template form to test the RSAC implementations

Subcomponent document	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2	Reviewer 3
InvenioRDM	OpenAire	INRIA	TBC
DANS	InvenioRDM	DataCite	TBC
Dagstuhl	swMATH	GWDG	TBC
Episciences	DANS	INRIA	TBC
swMath	Episciences	GDWG	TBC
OpenAire	Dagstuhl	DataCite	TBC

Introduction to template

This file is for the internal testers and invited guests to review each RSAC implementation on which feedback will be collected for the first round of tests.

This is a collective review and not an individual review. Please use comments to discuss the component with the developers and the other reviewers.

Note: some of the public beta/demo, github repositories are not the same as in the infrastructure internal system. They are intended for providing functionality rather than showing the actual integration to the infra's system.

General Information on component

- Software Component: XXXX
- Category: RSAC
- Contact Person (component):
- Email:
- Link to demo:
- Link to documentation:
- Other resources:
 - Deposit sprint results and items from deposit puzzle
 - Status update at M18

Review Check Date: | Version (of component):

	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2	Reviewer 3
Name			
email			
pseudo			

Questions & clarifications

Reviewer	Question	Answer

Functionalities

Please add the sequence diagram here with a mermaid instance (using Google add-on) or a png
 Please make sure it is the same sequence diagram shown in the SPECS

Are the post-conditions below met when using the tool?

Item to review	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2	Reviewer 3
First version			
Software record in component platform			
Software source code archived in SWH			
SWHID is available on component software record			
Which SWHID is used? Core / with context? snp, rel, rev, dir, cnt? Is this SWHID adapted to the use case and platform?			
Software metadata visible to the user with specific software metadata fields			
Are citation fields available, such as			
Title/name			

Item to review	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2	Reviewer 3
Authors			
Version			
Abstract/description			
Are there missing metadata fields?			
Metadata formats and citation available for export			
Which formats are available?			
Metadata is deposited in SWH			
N+1 version (content changed + metadata changed):			
Software record updated in component platform			
N+1 source code archived in SWH			
New SWHID is available on component software record			
New software metadata visible to the user with specific software metadata fields			
Metadata formats and citation available for export for N+1 metadata			
N+1 Metadata is deposited in SWH			

Free form feedback:

What to keep?

What to add?

What to change/delete?

topic	To keep	To add	To change/delete
Ex: SWHID			Use dir SWHID

UI review

Depending on the sequence diagram and the required view in the specs, verify if these views exists and comment if the views are easily accessible and that the user experience is adapted for the potential platform user

Is the web interface clear and easy to use (if applicable)?	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2	Reviewer 3
Landing page			
Login view			
Register view			
Archive functionality view			
Reference functionality view			
Describe functionality view			
Cite functionality view			

Free form feedback, all reviewers to insert input collectively in the table. Feel free to comment on other inserted input and name additional reviewers for feedback.

What to keep?

What to add?

What to change/delete?

Location	To keep	To add	To change/delete
----------	---------	--------	------------------

Ex: login view	Keep view as is		

Integration

Is the service integrated easily with other FC4E components? And identify how?

All components are described here: <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components>

This is a question mostly for devs in RSAC implementation teams and on the other FC4E teams. For example: resolution of a SWHID and other used identifiers for software

FC4E components	Possible integrations?	Divergences
CAT		
DTR		
MSCR		
PIDGraph		
PIDMR		
RAiD		
RDGRAPH		
SWHM		

Is the service integrated with other the services in the Open Science landscape

FC4E components	Possible integrations?
ORCID	
Schema.org	
CodeMeta	
SciCodes consortium	

FC4E components	Possible integrations?

Documentation Analysis

Documentation analysis	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2	Reviewer 3
Who is the audience of the available documentation?			
What is the topic of the available documentation? Which questions does it answer?			
Is it usable by the identified audience?			
Who is the audience of the available documentation?			
What is the topic of the available documentation? Which questions does it answer?			

- Free form feedback:
 - What to keep?
 - What to add?
 - What to change/delete?

Appendix E: The FAIRFEST poster for the RSAC and SWHM components

Building a community driven vision for Research Software: Connecting the scholarly ecosystem

FAIRCORE4EOSC's WP6 develops tools and services for archiving, referencing, describing, and citing research software. It aims to connect repositories, publishers, and aggregators via Software Heritage integration, CodeMeta, and Software Hash Identifiers (SWHID).

Software has multiple facets:

- a tool
- a research outcome
- the object of research

Implementing the Scholarly Infrastructures for Research Software (SIRS) report

Making Research Software FAIR in EOSC: The 2021 SIRS report recommended including software in the scholarly ecosystem alongside publications and data. Building on a survey of European research software infrastructures, the FAIRCORE4EOSC project is implementing these recommendations, focusing on:

- Improved collaboration between aggregators, publishers, repositories, and Software Heritage.
- Standardized metadata and tools.
- Wider use of PIDs (including SWHID)

- Three pillars of Open Science Software Heritage CC BY 4.0 2019
- Archive**
 - make sure we can access to retrieve the software (reproducibility)
 - Reference**
 - make sure we can identify the software artifacts (reproducibility)
 - Describe**
 - make it easy to discover the software projects (visibility)
 - Cite (for credit)**
 - make it rewarding to create software by giving credit to authors (evaluation)

Software to Forget? A software stack can contain:

1. Project specific code
2. Domain specific tools
3. Scientific infrastructure
4. Non-scientific infrastructure

Examples: Scripts, notebooks, SHARC, AMTC, ...; BLAS, HDF5, Sisyphus, ...; Git, Python, ...; Docker, ...

Konrad Hinsen: Dealing With Software Collapse, Computing in Science and Engineering, 2010, 21(1), pp.104-108. (10.1109/MCSE.2010.2939443). (doi:10.2177/389)

The Software Metadata Curation Roadmap

10.5281/zenodo.14509418

Towards a distributed and multistakeholder infrastructure: the EOSC Software Heritage Mirror (SWHM)

A mirror of the Software Heritage universal source code archive will be deployed in 2025 in Greece at GRNET. A mirror is a full copy the archive, operated in agreement with, but independently from the Software Heritage organization.

"Let us save what remains: not by vaults and locks which fence them from the public eye and use in consigning them to the waste of time, but by such a multiplication of copies, as shall place them beyond the reach of accident."

— Thomas Jefferson

The Research Software APIs and connectors (RSAC) components are enhancing Research Software services and connecting Software Heritage with key infrastructures:

- Scholarly repositories: Zenodo (CERN), DANS Dataverse's instance,
- Publishers: Dagstuhl, Episciences
- Aggregators: swMath, OpenAire & Datacite

SIRS report: European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Scholarly infrastructures for research software: report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Group (WG) Architecture Task Force TTF SIRS, Publications Office, 2020. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/28598>

Software preservation requires a **global** and **coordinated** effort.

Reflections on the Research Software infrastructures

Join the discussion on the EOSC OA7
 eosc OA Expert Group: Research Software

This boat represents your journey through Research Software infrastructures. Using the different situations, on a post-it, tell us more about where you are now and what are your plans in the Research Software journey.

Watch the demo of RSAC

RSAC
EOSC Research Software APIs & Connectors

SWHM
EOSC Software Heritage Mirror